

////////////////////////////////////

BALANCE BETWEEN BEAUTY AND USABILITY IN KANSEI INTERFACE FOR SMARTPHONE.

Hou, Kai-Chun / Ho, Chun-Heng / Lu, Yen-Nien
cage.hou@gmail.com / hoch@mail.ncku.edu.tw / k0912030458@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

A well-designed interface must be both usable and beautiful. A kansei interface additionally requires the ability to arouse positive emotions. The purpose of this paper is to illustrate the kansei interface that appears to be important determinants of acceptance for smartphone's apps. The concept of the "kansei interface" proposed by Yamazaki is extended to interface design of smartphone in this study. The way users evaluate applications on a smartphone was evaluated using direct observations, rating scales, and interviews. Some relationships between users and the interface were found.

Keywords: interface, kansei, usability.

INTRODUCTION

A well-designed interface must be both usable and beautiful (Hassenzahl & Ullrich, 2007). A beautiful product can evoke pleasant feelings and a usable interface allows smooth operation. Many studies have found the importance of usability. A usable interface is a fundamental consideration in the field of design. With the recent emphasis on visual user experience, beauty has gradually increased in importance and is now considered alongside usability (Hassenzahl, 2004; Lindgaard, 2007; Linghammar, 2007).

As mobile interfaces have become increasingly intuitive and easy to use, a huge number of applications (abbreviated as apps hereafter) have become available for smartphones. According to the latest survey (January 2011) by DISTIMO¹, the number mobile phone apps is more than 45 million.

The number of mobile app developers has increased with the demand for apps by users.

There are thus a large number of mobile apps that have similar functions but different interfaces. The selection of applications can be difficult for users. If an interface is difficult to use, the app can be easily replaced by one with similar functions.

This study determined users' feelings while operating a smartphone; which connect emotion and perceive by users that we called 'kansei' feeling form oriental culture (Dahlgaard, Schütte, Ayas, & Dahlgaard-Park, 2008; Ma, 2010). Kansei information included emotional, sensitive and the value creation perspective (Yuji & Hisao, 2009). Digital interfaces provide a way for users to communicate with technological products for finding information (Eikenes & Morrison, 2010). An emotional relationship between the user and an app with a kansei information aspect of interface is called the kansei interface (Hou & Ho, 2011). Usability and beauty are two important topics in the human-computer interface (HCI) field. Studies have found these two concepts to be essential design conditions in interactive design (Hassenzahl, 2004; Morrison, 2010; Overbeeke, Djajadiningrat, Hummels, & Wensveen, 2002).

This study discusses two kansei interface ideas: (1) in addition to usability and beauty, a kansei interface should arouse positive emotions and (2) a good kansei interface allows users to operate a smartphone without frustration. In the experiment phase, smartphone apps with similar functions that use different interfaces (text-based and metaphor, respectively) are considered.

¹ Distimo is an app store analytics company.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND KANSEI INTERFACE

Usability and beauty appear to have conflicting goals. However, using a set of psychological constructs, we can understand how users think about usability and beauty (Hassenzahl & Monk, 2010). Besides an interface being accurate and efficient, the diversity of the interface design also arouses some emotional consciousness to users (Tzvetanova, 2007). Previous studies suggest that interface designers should go back to the essence of people's life experiences, from an interactive aesthetics of point of view to think about the future of HCI, which is interaction with human emotional connection (Hummels & Overbeeke, 2010; Petersen, Iversen, Krogh, & Ludvigsen, 2004; Salem, Nakatsu, & Rauterberg, 2009). Salem et al. (2009) found that the perceptual experience (kansei experience) of users with communication products is a new experience, and that it evokes pleasant emotions. Furthermore, the information of relationship of communication between users and products can be defined a kinds of affective communication (Lei & Zhibin, 2010). People expect interacting with technology products to be fun, especially for web-based services, mobile devices, and consumer electronics (Shneiderman, 2004). Digital interface designers should thus pay more attention to improving interaction with the interface of a product.

The word 'kansei' used in this study does not refer to Kansei Engineering (KE) at all. It refers to emotion, sensitivity, affection, and intuition. Some scholars have used 'kansei' to represent positive emotion during interaction with products (Lee, Harada, & Stappers, 2002; Salem et al., 2009).

User-friendly interface means easy use and which emotional appeal with elements of conditions should inside (Eikenes & Morrison, 2010; Ngo, 2001). The concept of the kansei interface proposed by Yamazaki is extended to smartphones. This study found that a kansei interface for smartphones is not only usable and beautiful, but it can also arouse positive emotions.

The phenomenon of human visual is impressions that people almost have aesthetic cognition, which is fast, enduring and consequential (Tractinsky & Hassenzahl,

2005). Tractinsky (2005) found that people like to look at beautiful things and that beauty makes a strong impression on users. Figure 1 shows the main menu of apps with beautiful interfaces, which resulted of the study.

Figure 1. Screenshots of the main menus of (a) Awesome Note² and (b) Convertbot³.

Lindgaard(2007) found that users may be more satisfied with a beautiful product whose performance is relatively low than with a more usable product whose appeal is lower. The present study found that a kansei interface should have attractive elements to draw users' attention.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Developing an interface that balances usability and beauty is difficult. This study determined users' feelings while interacting with interfaces of smartphone apps. A web-based questionnaire with 18 (3 categories, 6 apps per category) app icons with various styles and interface screenshots was designed. The 32 participants (9 are design background and 23 are non-design background) were asked to rate these apps using the icons and interface screenshots in addition to price. The age distribution was between 20 and 40 years old. We developed a series of smartphone tasks and invited participants to carry out the tasks. A flowchart of the experiment is shown in Figure 2.

² Copyright ©2010 BRID.

³ Copyright ©2008-2011 TAPBOTS.

Figure 2. Flowchart of experiment.

Picking a suitable app for users is a series of procedures. The web-based questionnaire recorded and analyzed the users' selection behavior using the users' preference of icon design.

Direct observations, rating scales, and interviews were used in the task stage. We invited 10 participants (half had previous smartphone experience) to carry out the experiments. All procedures of task are task-oriented, and operation time is unlimited.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

During the smartphone experiments, the participants' operating behaviors and feelings were recorded. The apps of task-experiment were divided into an experimental group and a control group. The experimental group used apps with richly decorated interfaces and the control group used apps with neat interfaces. There were two interface design styles for each category, one relatively simple and the other decorated with images or metaphor. In this stage, three categories of commonly used apps were selected: note taking, unit conversion, and finance.

After the task stage, the participants filled out a questionnaire to rate emotions. The participants were asked to rate an interface on a usability and beauty scale ('U-B' scale). According to the interface

design guidelines, a basic interface should satisfy the usability and beauty which will be one of the conditions. This study evaluated approach is not the relative discussion between usability and beauty; instead of using the balance scale (U-B scale) to estimate the interface. The U-B scale allows a direct analysis of the kansei interface. More specifically, u-b scale provides a tool for participants to check the information of usability and beauty, but it still retains both characteristics based on usability and beauty in the interface. Figure 3 shows an example of the U-B scale in two forms.

Figure 3. Example of U-B scale. (a) Conventional U-B scale and (b) matrix form of U-B scale.

When rating an interface, participants be asked to give a ration between usability and beauty form their fist impression. It is the advantage of this intuitive survey that will not allow participants to think too much. We try to not use two independent variables (usability and beauty) of u-b scale, for participants avoid considering too much at one time with two variables. The u-b scale is also easier to understand the true feelings of the participants.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 4 shows the results of the web-based questionnaire. The majority of users selected software based on icon design. Colorful icons with a simple style attracted the most users; and some decorated text, rich pattern also have attractiveness for users. However, nearly half of the users could not decide on software based on the icon.

Figure 4. Results of web-based questionnaire.

Figure 5 shows the average number of steps required to complete each task. Note-B (53%), Money-B (65%), and Convert-A (73%) apps require more steps (also more spend time) to complete tasks than do the other apps in their respectively categories. These 3 apps all use many decorative elements.

Figure 5. Average number of steps required to complete tasks.

Participants' operation behavior was recorded on video. Although beautiful interfaces required more time to use, participants still preferred them.

Figure 6. Results of operating experience for note-taking apps.

Figure 6 shows the results of operation experience for note-taking apps. Participants prefer Note-B. From interviews, the main reason for this preference was the colorful interface. The rich design elements allow participants to find target notes easily. The participants also found Note-B pleasant to use.

Figure 7. Results of operating experience for unit conversion apps.

Figure 7 shows the operating experience results for unit conversion apps. Participants prefer Convert-A because of its robot-like theme even though they required more steps and time to complete the task. Convert-A also provides sound feedback, which makes interaction fun, interesting, and attractive. But there still a few participants lose their patience in operating the convert-A app.

Figure 8. Results of operating experience for finance apps.

Figure 8 shows the results of operating experience for finance apps. The two apps have similar values. Both apps use a metaphor design for the interface. Money-A looks similar to a money book that is commonly used in oriental culture whereas Money-B uses a more abstract interface that is full of image decorations. Results show that participants lost patience with Money-B (dotted circle in the figure). Participants prefer beauty to usability, but the interface should not be over-decorated.

The results of the task experiment are shown in Figure 9. Figure 9 (a) shows the mean preference of users for interface styles in terms of usability and beauty. These apps interface was divided to each page, which can be estimated detailed by participants. The results show that there is a significant difference between usability and beauty

(all p-values/2 < $\alpha=0.05$, see Table 1). It's evident that the perspective of participants is quite different for usability and beauty. See table1.

Interface		Mean	SD	t-value	p-value
Note-taking app	A01-B01	-2.600	1.075	-7.649	.000
	A02-B02	-1.900	1.101	-5.460	.000
	A03-B03	-2.600	1.075	-7.649	.000
Unit conversion app	A01-B01	2.600	.966	8.510	.000
	A02-B02	2.800	.919	9.635	.000
Finance app	A01-B01	-2.000	1.333	-4.743	.001
	A02-B02	-2.200	.789	-8.820	.000
	A03-B03	-1.300	1.059	-3.881	.004

$\alpha= 0.05$; $df = 9$

Table 1. t-test results for usability and beauty.

Simple neat interfaces obtained high usability values whereas richly decorated interfaces obtained high beauty values, as shown in Figure 9(a). In general, the usability values are higher than the beauty values.

Figure 9(a) shows an overview of evaluation in usability and beauty. Figure 9(b) shows that participant preferences. Most participants preferred beautiful interfaces after carrying out all tasks.

Interview results show that participants are willing to spend time to adapt to a beautiful interface because the participants enjoyed some surprising element (sophisticated icon, smooth animation, and melodious sound) in operation. Sense of these surprises by metaphor design in interface can reduce the frustration of the operation of participants. This result is consistent with that in the study of Lindgaard.

CONCLUSION

This study found that users prefer beauty to usability for smartphone apps. A usability-beauty scale was used to rate app interfaces more directly and more easily. Results show that beauty motivates operation.

It was also found that a kansei interface can provide good, comfortable operation. It allows users to

Figure 9. Results of task experiment. (a) Mean preferences of users of usability and beauty for interface styles. (b) Results of preferences. Smile face means participants' preference degree. All comparison values have a statistically significant difference in usability and beauty for the two test interfaces.

tolerate a longer operating time and promotes learning. In addition, the kansei interface allows users to adapt to the interface without frustration and arouse users positive emotion for some cases.

REFERENCES

- Dahlgaard, J. J., Schütte, S., Ayas, E., & Dahlgaard-Park, S. M. (2008). Kansei/affective engineering design: A methodology for profound affection and attractive quality creation. *The TQM Journal*, 20(4)(Kansei/affective engineering design), 14.
- Eikenes, J. O. H., & Morrison, A. (2010). Navimation: Exploring Time, Space & Motion in the Design of Screen Based Interfaces. [Animation, Communication Design, Interface, Movement, Navigation, Social Semiotics.]. *International Journal of Design*.
- Hassenzahl, M. (2004). The interplay of beauty, goodness, and usability in interactive products. *Human-Computer Interaction*, 19(4), 319-349. doi: 10.1207/s15327051hci1904_2
- Hassenzahl, M., & Monk, A. (2010). The Inference of Perceived Usability From Beauty. *Human-Computer Interaction*, 25(3), 235 - 260.
- Hassenzahl, M., & Ullrich, D. (2007). To do or not to do: Differences in user experience and retrospective judgments depending on the presence or absence of instrumental goals. *Interacting with Computers*, 19(4), 429-437. doi: DOI: 10.1016/j.intcom.2007.05.001
- Hou, K.-C., & Ho, C.-H. (2011). Previous studies of Relationship with Kansei Interface between user and smartphone applications. Paper presented at the 6th International Conference on Planning and Design, Tainan.
- Hummels, C., & Overbeeke, K. (2010). Aesthetics of Interaction. *International Journal of Design*, 4(2).
- Kosaka, Y., & Shiizuka, H. (2009). A method for creating buying behavior of customer by kansei information design. *Journal of Modelling in Management*, 4(1), 19-27. doi:10.1108/17465660910943739
- Lee, S., Harada, A., & Stappers, P. J. (2002). Pleasure with Products: Design based on Kansei. Paper presented at the Beyond usability, London.
- Lei, S., & Zhibin, X. (2010, 22-23 May 2010). Designing Product to Improve Affective Communication. Paper presented at the Intelligent Systems and Applications (ISA), 2010 2nd International Workshop on.
- Lindgaard, G. (2007). Aesthetics, Visual Appeal, Usability and User Satisfaction: What Do the User's Eyes Tell the User's Brain? *Australian Journal of Emerging Technologies and Society*, 5(1), 1-14.
- Linghammar, F. (2007). Usability and Aesthetics. Linköping University.
- Ma, M.-Y. (2010). Dive into the Consumers' World: The Introduction of New Product Development in Japan. *Industrial Materials*, 280, 160-172.
- Morrison, J. O. H. E. A. (2010). Navimation: Exploring Time, Space & Motion in the Design of Screen Based Interfaces. *International Journal of Design*, 4(1)(Aesthetics of Interaction), 16.
- Ngo, D. C. L. (2001). Measuring the aesthetic elements of screen designs. *Displays*, 22(3), 73-78. doi: Doi: 10.1016/s0141-9382(01)00053-1
- Overbeeke, C., Djajadiningrat, J., Hummels, C., & Wensveen, S. (2002). Beauty in usability: forget about ease of use. Pleasure with products: Beyond usability., 9-18.
- Petersen, M. G., Iversen, O. S., Krogh, P. G., & Ludvigsen, M. (2004). Aesthetic interaction: a pragmatist's aesthetics of interactive systems. Paper presented at the Proceedings of the 5th conference on Designing interactive systems: processes, practices, methods, and techniques, Cambridge, MA, USA.
- Salem, B., Nakatsu, R., & Rauterberg, M. (2009). Kansei experience: Aesthetic, emotions and inner balance. *International Journal on Cognitive Intelligence and Natural Intelligence*, 3, 18-36.
- Shneiderman, B. (2004). Designing for fun: how can we design user interfaces to be more fun? *interactions*, 11(5), 48-50. doi: 10.1145/1015530.1015552
- Tractinsky, N., & Hassenzahl, M. (2005). Arguing for Aesthetics in Human-Computer Interaction. *i-com*, 4(3), 3.
- Tzvetanova, S. (2007). Emotional Interface Methodology. Paper presented at the lasdr 07 international association of societies of design research, Hong Kong.
- YAMAZAKI, K. (2003). Structure for Kansei Interface Design. Paper presented at the 6th Asian Design Conference 2003, Tsukuba.